

ANALYSIS ON DATA WITH FATIGUE 3-4-5

Number of trials per stimulus mode					
	0	100	140	180	Total
None	67	-	-	-	67
AudioOnly	-	61	66	71	198
VisualsOnly	-	62	66	72	200
Both	-	67	65	65	197
Total	67	190	197	208	662

Stimuli type and performance

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: correctNormalized

ANOVA correctNormalized~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
2.179	0.0893	

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.9994646	1.0107092	-0.68928	0.4928

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.9929803	1.0120461	-2.3337	0.01998

T-TEST correctNormalized~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
1.0051727	0.9938203	1.3845	0.1668

TukeyHSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
Both-Audi	-0.01465177	-0.0409195	0.0116159	0.4768831
None-Audi	-0.00178938	-0.038729	0.0351503	0.9993057
VisualsOnly	-0.02433600	-0.0505379	0.0018659	0.0795526
None-Both	0.012862386	-0.0240773	0.0498020	0.8064996
VisualsOnly	-0.00968422	-0.0358862	0.0165177	0.7767005
VisualsOnly	-0.02254661	-0.0594395	0.0143463	0.3942075

Stimuli tempo and performance

Parameter: tempo | Variable: correctNormalized | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo		
F	p	
0.571	0.634	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.327	0.722	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
1.242	0.291	

ANOVA correctNormalized~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
0.66	0.518	

Stimuli type and time estimation

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception)

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.45	0.717	

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.0063116	0.0183417	-0.35755	0.7215

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.0153530	-0.0041919	0.84861	0.3964

T-TEST deltaTimePerception~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.0046215	0.0118307	-0.30602	0.7597

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~stimulusTrial		
F	p	
0.246	0.864	

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasStimulusTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.2069562	0.1964091	0.48109	0.6316

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasVisualTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.2107467	0.1986109	0.73918	0.4601

T-TEST abs(deltaTimePerception)~hasAudioTrial			
mean Has-No	t	p	
0.2025121	0.2108840	-0.49654	0.6197

Stimuli tempo and time estimation

Parameter: tempo | Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception) | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo		
F	p	
1.783	0.149	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
2.551	0.0806	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.296	0.744	

ANOVA deltaTimePerception~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
1.172	0.312	

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
100-0	-0.00434598	-0.1042085	0.0955166	0.9994969
140-0	-0.05616969	-0.1556464	0.0433071	0.4663147
180-0	0.010672619	-0.0890426	0.1103878	0.9926922
140-100	-0.05182370	-0.1215673	0.0179199	0.2233741
180-100	0.015018609	-0.0550646	0.0851018	0.9461046
180-140	0.066842312	-0.0026901	0.1363747	0.0646654

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
140-100	-0.0854566	-0.2034623	0.0325490	0.2038930
180-100	0.0170854	-0.0989073	0.1330781	0.9354927
180-140	0.1025420	-0.0110628	0.2161469	0.0861183

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo		
F	p	
1.797	0.146	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterAUDIOONLY]		
F	p	
0.633	0.532	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterVISUALONLY]		
F	p	
0.366	0.694	

ANOVA abs(deltaTimePerception)~tempo [filterBOTH]		
F	p	
2.354	0.0977	

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
140-100	-0.0389901	-0.1332075	0.0552273	0.5920165
180-100	0.0480553	-0.0461621	0.1422727	0.4518505
180-140	0.0870454	-0.0078830	0.1819739	0.0797455

Stimuli type and time judgment

Parameters: stimulusTrial, hasAudioTrial, hasVisualTrial, hasStimulusTrial | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~classes			
chi-2	df	p	
6.7609	3	0.07992	

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasStimulusTrial			
W	p		
23562	0.01089		
mean Has	mean Not		
3.522689	3.164179		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasAudioTrial			
W	p		
54612	0.4177		
mean Has	mean Not		
3.513924	3.445693		

WILCOXON reportedSpeedPerception~hasVisualTrial			
W	p		
56131	0.1275		
mean Has	mean Not		
3.534005	3.415094		

paired WILCOXON		
AudioOnly	Both	None
Both	0.776	-

None	0.065	0.053	-
VisualsOnI	0.776	0.975	0.053

Stimuli tempo and time judgment

Parameter: tempo | Variable: reportedSpeedPerception | Filters: filterAUDIOONLY, filterVISUALONLY, filterBOTH

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo			
chi-2	df	p	
8.9421	3	0.03007	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo[filterAUDIOONLY]			
chi-2	df	p	
2.0739	2	0.3545	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo[filterVISUALS]			
chi-2	df	p	
0.038721	2	0.9808	

KRUSKAL-WALLIS reportedSpeedPerception~tempo[filterBOTH]			
chi-2	df	p	
2.7482	2	0.2531	

paired WILCOXON			
	0	100	140
100	0.193	-	-
140	0.032	0.193	-
180	0.040	0.321	0.672

Correlations time judgment - estimation - performance

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized

PEARSON deltaTimePerception~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.10932378	0.04290988	0.0334006	

PEARSON abs(deltaTimePerception)~correctNormalized			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1377377	0.0140789	0.0621891	

SPEARMAN deltaTimePerception~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
-0.2561829	2.217e-11	

SPEARMAN abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
0.1363082	0.0004366	

SPEARMAN correctNormalized~reportedSpeedPerception		
rho	p	
0.1589975	3.915e-05	

Confounding effects of fatigue

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), reportedSpeedPerception, correctNormalized, reportedFatigue

ANOVA correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
2.768	0.0635	

Anova deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
0.365	0.694	

Anova abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
F	p	
0.774	0.462	

TUKEY HSD				
diff	lwr	upr	p adj	
4-3	0.01121002	-1.136611e	0.0337861	0.4737435
5-3	0.02284141	3.551909e	0.0456473	0.0495419
5-4	0.01163139	-1.102368e	0.0342864	0.4500043

Spearman correctNormalized~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.0849293	0.02877	

Spearman deltaTimePerception~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.0008916	0.9817	

Spearman abs(deltaTimePerception)~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.0661864	0.08883	

Spearman reportedSpeedPerception~reportedFatigue		
rho	p	
0.2152119	2.185e-08	

Confounding effects of trial index

Variables: deltaTimePerception, abs(deltaTimePerception), correctNormalized, trialIndex

Pearson correctNormalized~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
0.03868216	0.1889850	0.1144888	

Pearson deltaTimePerception~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
0.0069063	0.1582635	0.0830639	

Pearson abs(deltaTimePerception)~trialIndex			
95% CI	cor	p	
-0.1477075	0.0039026	-0.0723202	